

Terpenoids: Part XXXVI. A Convenient route for the Syntheses of Isopropenylic Terpenes

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Through the application of lithium vinyl copper reagent, a new method of synthesising isopropenylic terpenes has been developed. Based upon this technique, the new and facile syntheses of β -terpineol, (\pm), carvestrene, (\pm) dipentene, (\pm) 1-methyl-4-isopropenyl cyclohexane and (\pm) isopulegone have been achieved.

One of the most generally used method for the unambiguous fixation of double bond in the isopropenylic form is the well known Wittig reaction¹ with methylene triphenylphosphorane² which has been employed by Vig et al. in accomplishing the unambiguous syntheses of many terpenoids.³⁻⁷

Another equally potential synthetic approach for the creation of this type of methylenic bond utilised profusely is the Claisen rearrangement reaction⁸. This involves the pyrolysis of the appropriate vinyl ether prepared from suitably constituted allylic alcohol through the freshly-crystallised mercuric-acetate catalysed⁹ trans-etherification reaction with alkyl-vinyl ether to provide the unsaturated aldehyde with the desired methylenic bond. Employing this technique, the syntheses of carvone¹⁰, dihydrocarvone¹¹, perillaldehyde¹² and 2, 6-dimethyl- Δ^3 -octenone¹³ have been effected in our laboratory.

Besides the above two techniques, we made use of another method based upon the hydrogenolysis reaction¹⁴ of suitably substituted β -allylic carbinols with sodium and ethanol in anhydrous liquid ammonia for the syntheses of isopropenylic terpenes.^{15, 16}

With the discovery of lithium vinyl copper as synthetic reagent¹⁷, a new field has been opened for the direct attachment of isopropenyl grouping at the suitable position in a terpenoid. Analogous to the methyl copper which has been represented as $\text{Li}^+(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Cu}^-$

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4. O. P. Vig, K. L. Matta, Romesh Anand and Inder Raj, *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 841.
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9. W. S. Watanable and L. E. Conlon; *Ibid*, 1957, **78**, 2828.
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11. O. P. Vig, S. D. Sharma, Suresh Chander and Inder Raj, *Ibid*, 1965, **3**, 425.
12. O. P. Vig, S. D. Sharma and Inder Raj, *Ibid*, 1966, **4**, 127.
13. O. P. Vig, K. L. Matta and Inder Raj, *This Journal*, 1964, **41**, 752.
14. A. J. Birch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 809; A. Eschermoser, J. Schreiber and W. Keller; *Helv. Chim. Acta*; 1951, **34**, 1667; A. J. Birch, and (Miss) A. R. Murray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1888.
15. O. P. Vig, Amrik Lal and K. L. Matta; *This Journal* (in press).
16. O. P. Vig, J. P. Salota, M. P. Sharma and S. D. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, No. 4.
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by Corey and Posner¹⁸, the isopropenyl copper can be assigned the structure

$\text{Li}^+ \left(\overset{\text{C}}{\text{CH}_3 \text{CH}_2} \right)_2 \text{Cu}^-$. The reagent was obtained by the addition of anhydrous cuprous iodide to isopropenyl lithium (prepared from 2-bromopropene and lithium metal in dry tetrahydrofuran) below 0° in the molar ratio of 1 : 2 and most of the vinylations were performed below -5° with five moles of the copper reagent per mole of the halide derivative. The complex, thus generated, reacted sharply with suitable halides to furnish the desired terpenic molecules.

Our experiments have shown that this new technique is a simple, high yielding step and the presence of ester or ketonic group in the reacting halide does not cause any interference and the double bond in the isopropenyl group of terpenic molecules is fixed beyond any doubt even under energetically unfavourable circumstances.

The present investigations are directed towards the syntheses of the following compounds through the application of this new approach.

Preparation of Methyl-styrene (I) : As a part of our studies, we piloted the reaction

of $\text{Li}^+ \left(\overset{\text{C}}{\text{CH}_3 \text{CH}_2} \right)_2 \text{Cu}^-$ with bromobenzene to obtain methyl-styrene(I) in

quantitative yield.

The compound(I) was chromatographed over alumina and was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The purity was checked by t.l.c. which showed a single visible spot. Another sample of methyl-styrene was prepared from acetophenone by employing the Wittig reaction with methylene triphenylphosphorane by the method of Corey². The I. R. absorption spectra of hydrocarbon (I) prepared by these two different methods were found to be identical.

Synthesis of β -Terpineol (II) : β -Terpineol, a monocyclic monoterpene tertiary alcohol, occurs in nature in the *nutmeg oil*¹⁹ and has been assigned the constitution (II) depending upon its physical and chemical properties²⁰. The structure has been confirmed through a synthesis achieved by Vig et al⁵. However, in the present studies, a new and elegant synthesis of this carbinol has been effected on the following lines.

The ketal-ketone (VII), prepared as given in literature²¹, was reduced to the corresponding alcohol (VIII) with lithium aluminium hydride. Reaction of this carbinol (VIII) with phosphorous tribromide in dry benzene afforded the keto-bromide(IV) which was

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19. Lee, Kauffman, Hartan and Liezabitowski, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, **58**, 4974 d.

20. A. R. Pinder, "The Chemistry of Terpenes", Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1960, p-51.

21. O. P. Vig, J. P. Salota, M. P. Sharma and S. D. Sharma, *This Journal* (in press).

subjected to the reaction of lithium vinyl copper to obtain 4-isopropenyl cyclohexanone (X). The ketone was confirmed through the formation of yellow D.N.P. (m.p. 129-30°).

The ketone (X) on submission to Grignard reaction with methyl magnesium bromide furnished β -terpineol(II). The structure was confirmed through the identical I.R. spectrum with our previous synthetic sample of β -terpineol⁵.

Synthesis of (\pm) Carvestrene(III): Carvestrene, a monocyclic monoterpene hydrocarbon, is found to occur in the racemic form²². As a result of comprehensive studies²³⁻²⁵ on the constitution of carvestrene, expression (III) was suggested for this hydrocarbon.

The first unambiguous synthesis of this hydrocarbon was achieved in our laboratory¹⁶. Reaction of lithium di-isopropenyl copper on the halide (XI) affords a new single step synthesis of (\pm) carvestrene (III).

The hydrocarbon (III) was chromatographed over alumina and was confirmed to be a single product by t.l.c. The identity was supported by the superimposable I.R. spectrum with the synthesised sample¹⁶.

22. A. R. Pinder, "The Chemistry of Terpenes", Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1960, pp. 79, 80.
23. I. I. Bardishev, *C. R. Acad. Sci. U. S. S. R.* 1953, 90(6), 1305.
24. M. I., Batuerc, I. I. Bardeshev and A. D. Matabeeba; *Bull. Acad. Sci. U. S. S. R.*, 1958, 323.
25. M. C. Punnoose and James Verghese; *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 229.

Synthesis of (\pm) Dipentene (IV): This is the most widely distributed monoterpene hydrocarbon in various terpenes.²⁶ The structure (IV) for this compound has been established *via* degradation²⁶ and synthesis²⁷.

The present synthetic route, based upon the application of this new approach records another unambiguous synthesis of this hydrocarbon.

The product was chromatographed and the structure established (*vide Infra*)²⁷.

Synthesis of (\pm) 1-Methyl-4-isopropenyl-cyclohexane (V): 1-Methyl-4-isopropenyl cyclohexane (V) has been reported to be the product of Wolf-Kishner reduction of dihydrocarvone.²⁸ Vig et al. have already reported a five-step synthesis¹⁵ of this compound starting from 1-Methyl-4-bromo-cyclohexane, whereas the application of lithium divinyl copper on the same starting material afforded the hydrocarbon (V) in a single step.

The synthetic hydrocarbon was chromatographed over alumina for purification. Its I. R. spectra was found to be superimposable with our previously prepared sample.¹⁵

Synthesis of (\pm) Isopulegone (VI): Isopulegone, a monocyclic monoterpene ketone, occurs along with pulegone in essential oils²⁹. The structure (VI) has been assigned on the basis of chemical evidence, spectral data and its relationship to isopulegol and pulegone.²⁹

A synthesis of this ketone has been reported by the application of Wittig reaction⁴. In the present investigations depending upon the findings that the presence of a keto group does not cause any interference in lithium vinyl copper reaction, we report an elegant synthesis of (\pm) isopulegone from 2-bromo-5-methyl-cyclohexanone (XIV).

26. A. R. Pinder, "The Chemistry of Terpenes", Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1960, pp. 42-47.

27. O. P. Vig, K. L. Matta, Gurdeep Singh and Inder Raj, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 25.

28. E. H. Rodd., "Chemistry of Carbon Compounds", Elsevier Pub. Co., New York, Pt. B-11, 537.

29. A. R. Pinder, "The Chemistry of the Terpenes", Chapman and Hall Ltd., London, 1960, pp. 60, 69.

The reaction product was purified by chromatography which on elution with pet. ether: benzene (4 : 1) yielded the ketone (VI) which was confirmed through the formation of yellow D.N.P. (m.p. 134-35°). The structure was further supported through the comparable I.R. Spectra⁴.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Methyl-styrene(I) : 2-bromopropene (7.8 g.) in dry T.H.F. (15 ml.) was added dropwise to a well stirred mixture of lithium (0.89 g.) in dry T.H.F. (50 ml.) kept under an atmosphere of nitrogen. After the complete dissolution of lithium metal, the contents were cooled below 0° and anhydrous cuprous iodide (6.5 g.) was added in small lots. The resulting product was stirred below 0° for about ½ hr. followed by the dropwise addition of bromobenzene (1.0 g.) in T.H.F. (10 ml.) and the contents were kept at the same temperature for further 6 hr. The slurry thus obtained was decomposed with ice-cold water and the product extracted with (3 × 100 ml.) ether. The combined extract was washed with water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent and subsequently distillation of the product furnished methyl-styrene (1), b.p. 80-90°/15 mm., yield 0.6 g. (80%).

I.R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 2950 cm^{-1} (C-Me), 1650, 1600 (diene), 3050, 1650 and 890 cm^{-1} ($\frac{R_1}{R_2} > \text{C} = \text{CH}_2$) and 740, 690, 680 cm^{-1} (phenyl) are identical to the second sample of methyl-styrene prepared from acetophenone through the application of Wittig reaction. (Found: C, 91.19; H, 8.16; C_9H_{10} requires C, 91.52; H, 8.48%).

4 : 4*Ethylenedioxy-cyclohexanol* (VIII) : Ketal-ketone (VI; 9.0 g) in anhydrous ether (60 ml.) was added dropwise to a well stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.7 g.) in dry ether (100 ml.) during 1 hr. so as to maintain ether at a gentle reflux. After the addition was complete, the contents were stirred well for an additional 2 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and decomposed with a saturated solution of sodium sulphate. The organic layer was separated and aqueous layer extracted thrice with ether. The combined ethereal extract was washed with water and dried. After removing the solvent, the residual oil was vacuum distilled to afford (VIII) as a colourless oil, b.p. 120-27°/4 mm. (reported³¹ b.p. 103-04°/0.5 mm.), yield 6.5 g. (72%), η^{23}_D 1.4845 (reported³¹ η^{22}_D 1.4840).

*All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent. The I. R. spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer fitted with a grating. Microanalysis were performed by Mr. B. N. Anand, Microanalyst, Panjab University, Chandigarh-14. All the vinylations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere. 2-bromopropene used was purified according to the procedure of House et al.³⁰

30. Herbert O. House, William L. Reepess and George M. Whitesides, *Ibid*, 1966, **31**, 3128.

31. D. A. Prins, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1957, **40**, 1626.

32. O.P. Vig, Suresh Chander, (Miss) Jasbir Puri and S. D. Sharma, *This Journal* (in press).

I.R. spectrum depicted characteristic bands at 3450 (-OH), 1145, 1105 (C-O) and 1065, 1040, and 1005 cm^{-1} (-OH) comparable to those reported³¹ at 3460, 1145, 1105, 1070, 1043 and 1005 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 60.16; H, 8.69; $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 60.74; H, 8.92%).

4-Bromo-cyclohexanone (IX): A mixture of the carbinol (VIII; 6.0 g.), thiophene free dried benzene (30 ml.) and four drops of pyridine was chilled in an ice-salt bath. To this was added phosphorous tribromide (5.0 g.) dropwise during 80 minutes. The reaction mixture was allowed to attain room temperature during 6 hr. and kept overnight. Finally it was heated at 60-65° for 2 hr. Thereafter, the contents were cooled and poured slowly with stirring into ice water. The decomposed product was allowed to stand for some time and the organic layer was separated. The aqueous mass was extracted thoroughly with ether four times. The combined benzene ether extract was shaken repeatedly with 10% hydrochloric acid to ensure complete deketalisation. The extract was washed with saturated sodium chloride solution and dried. The solvent was expelled off and the residue distilled under diminished pressure to give the keto-bromide (IX), b.p. 95-100°/5 mm., yield 2.9 g. (45%) (Found: C, 40.21; H, 4.88; Br, 44.67; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{BrO}$ requires C, 40.67; H, 5.09 and Br, 45.19%).

4-Isopropenyl-cyclohexanone (X): Reaction of lithium isopropenyl copper, prepared from 2-bromo-propene (7.0 g.), lithium (0.8 g.) and cuprous iodide (5.5 g.), on the keto-bromide (IX; 2.0 g.) following the same conditions already described under (I) provided 4-isopropenyl-cyclohexanone (X), b.p. 100°/10 mm., yield 1.1 g. (65%), η_{D}^{31} 1.4810.

I.R. spectrum showed prominent bands at 3060, 2950, 1720, 1440, 1365, 1230 and 890 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 78.61; H, 9.86; $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 78.21; H, 10.24%).

The ketone (X) formed yellow 2,4-D.N.P. which after crystallisation from ethanol melted at 120-30 (lit.³² reports m.p. 130-31°) (Found: N, 17.86, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ requires N, 17.61%).

1-Methyl-1-hydroxy-4-isopropenyl-cyclohexane (II): Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium (0.7 g.) and methyl iodide (5.0 g.) in dry ether (70 ml.). This was cooled in ice-cold water and the ketone (X; 1.0 g.) in dry ether (15 ml.) was added dropwise with constant stirring. After the addition was complete, the contents were left overnight and thereafter refluxed for 2 hr. to complete the reaction. The cooled contents were decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted many times with ether. The total ether extract was dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed. The residue on distillation gave β -terpineol (II) as a colourless material, b.p. 100°/7 mm., yield 0.8 g. (70%). It crystallises on chilling into a solid material, m.p. 30-31° (reported⁵ m.p. 32.33°).

I. R. spectrum (liquid film) showed peaks at 3450, 3100, 2980, 1650, 1450, 1360, 1250, 1190, 1140, 1090, 1045, 960, and 890 cm^{-1} . Lit.⁵ records peaks at 3460, 3135, 2980, 1650, 1450, 1360, 1250, 1190, 1130, 1095, 1040, 952 and 888 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 77.68; H, 11.65; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires C, 77.86; H, 11.68%).

3-Methyl-1-isopropenyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexene (III): 3-Methyl-1-bromo- Δ^2 -cyclohexene (XI; 1.0 g.) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of lithium di-isopropenyl copper prepared from lithium (0.8 g.), bromo-propene (7.0 g.) and cuprous iodide (5.5 g.) below 0°.

After the usual working up, (\pm) carvestrene (III; 0.6 g.) was obtained in 76 percent yield, η_D^{30} 1.4950 (reported¹⁶ η_D^{30} 1.4955).

I. R. spectrum of the synthetic product showed bands at 3050, 2980, 1775, 1650, 1600, 1610, 1450, 1370, 1200, 955, 890, 815, 775 and 700 cm^{-1} . Lit.¹⁶ records bands at 3050, 2990, 1770, 1650, 1600, 1610, 1450, 1370, 1190, 950, 890, 815, 780 and 700 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 88.20; H, 11.70; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$ requires C, 88.24; H, 11.76%).

1-Methyl-4-isopropenylcyclohexene (IV): 1-Methyl-4-bromo-cyclohex-1-ene (XII) was subjected to the reaction of lithium di-isopropenyl copper exactly according to the conditions cited in the synthesis of (\pm) carvestrene affording 0.62 g. (80%) of dipentene (IV), b.p. 55°/2-3 mm., η_D^{20} 1.4735 (Lit.² η_D^{20} 1.4730).

Infra-red spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 3060, 3000, 1660, 1460, 1375, 890, 810 and 790 cm^{-1} comparable to those reported in lit.²⁷. (Found: C, 88.09; H, 11.65; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$ requires C, 88.24; H, 11.76%).

4-Methyl-1-isopropenyl-cyclohexane (V): Vinyl lithium was prepared from Li (0.8 g.) and 2-bromopropene (7.0 g.) in dry T. H. F. under nitrogen. To this was added cuprous iodide (5.5 g.) below 0°. The vinylation was carried out with 1.0 g. of 4-methyl-1-bromocyclohexane (XIII) as described in (I). Work up in the usual way and chromatography over alumina provided (\pm) 4-methyl-1-isopropenyl-cyclohexane (V, 0.65 g.) (80 percent); b.p. 65°/15 mm., η_D^{25} 1.4500 (lit.¹⁵ η_D^{25} 1.445).

I. R. bands at 3080, 2980, 1650, 1450, 1375, 970 and 890 cm^{-1} are comparable to those reported in our earlier synthesis¹⁵. (Found: C, 86.62; H, 13.05; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}$ requires C, 86.88; H, 13.12%).

2-Isopropenyl-5-methyl-cyclohexanone (VI): Lithium di-isopropenyl copper was prepared from lithium (0.45 g.), 2-bromo-propene (4.0 g.) and cuprous iodide (3.5 g.) in the usual manner. This was cooled below -5° and 1.0 g. of 2-bromo-5-methyl-cyclohexanone (XIV, 10 g.) was added slowly with stirring. Usual working up afforded (\pm) isopulegone, b.p. 70°/4 mm., yield 0.5 g. (58%). The ketone (V) was purified by chromatography (eluent being; pot. ether: benzene: 4:1), η_D^{26} 1.4750 (lit.⁴ η_D^{20} 1.4675).

I. R. spectrum showed peaks at 3080, 2960, 1715, 1650, 1450, 1370, 1240 and 890 cm^{-1} identical to the one reported earlier.⁴ (Found: C, 78.57; H, 10.27; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires C, 78.60; H, 10.40%) 2: 4-DNP of (VI) melted at 135-36° (from ethanol). Lit.⁴ records m.p. 136-37°. (Found: N, 16.70, $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 16.80%).

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